

ARCTIC PASSION

Communication plan

Deliverable 9.1

Version 2

December 10, 2021

101003472 | Arctic PASSION

Work package

09 - Connecting the PAN-AOSS
with society through communication,
dissemination and engagement

Lead beneficiary

13 - GRID-Arendal

Lead authors

Sabrina Heerema (GRID-Arendal)
Anna Sinisalo (GRID-Arendal)
Lisa Grosfeld (APECS)
Josefine Lenz (APECS)

Contributors

Tero Mustonen (Snowchange)
Elaina Ford (BAS)
Tahnee Prior (WoA)
Michael Karcher (AWI)
Luisa Cristini (AWI)
Hasan Abbas (GRID-Arendal)
Elise Gunstvedt (GRID-Arendal)

Status

Final draft

Dissemination level

PU

This project has received funding from the
European Union's Horizon 2020 research
and innovation programme under grant
agreement No. 101003472

Document Revision History

<u>Date</u>	<u>Issue</u>	<u>Change records</u>	<u>Authors</u>
<u>2021-12-10</u>	<u>1.0</u>	<u>Submitted version 1.0 to the EU</u>	<u>Sabrina Heerema and Anna Sinisalo, GRID-Arendal; Lisa Grosfeld and Josefine Lens, AWI</u>
<u>2023-08-10</u>	<u>2.0</u>	<u>Revised version 2.0 submitted: The number and names of the Indigenous Peoples' Partner Communities were updated in the document; New partners were added to the list of abbreviations, the list of target audiences was updated in Section 3; Horizon Results Booster and Catalyst platform were added to section 5.2.16 European Commission tools; Table 8 was updated with qualitative KPIs; Windows to the Arctic was updated to Arctic Window throughout the document</u>	<u>Sabrina Heerema and Anna Sinisalo, GRID-Arendal; Lisa Grosfeld</u>

Commented [1]: I think it is enough to say it like this in this cell of the table

Table of Contents

Executive summary 5
Abbreviations used in the Work Package 9 plans: 5
1 Introduction 7
2 Arctic PASSION's communication objectives 8
 3 Arctic PASSION target audiences 9
4 Arctic PASSION's communication strategy for each target audience 12
5 Arctic PASSION's communication tools 18
 5.1 Tools for internal communications 18
 5.1.2 Intranet 18
 5.2 Tools for external communications 18
 5.2.1 Website 18

Project: Arctic PASSION

Deliverable 9.1 – Communication Plan

Website operations and responsibilities	19
5.2.2 Mailing lists	20
5.2.3 Social media	20
Social media strategy	20
Social media roles and responsibilities	22
5.2.4 Media outreach	23
Media outreach strategy	24
Potential News Outlets to Target	25
Media outreach responsibilities	26
5.2.5 Roll-ups, flyers and posters	27
5.2.6 International conferences, events, workshops and stakeholder meetings	27
5.2.7 EU Polar Cluster	28
5.2.8 Targeted briefings for policymakers	29
5.2.9 Training activities	29
5.2.10 Videos and vlogs	29
5.2.11 Windows to the Arctic platform	29
5.2.12 Arctic PASSION Newsletter and other newsletters	30
5.2.13 Online seminars	30
5.2.14 Stakeholder meetings	30
5.2.15 Communications toolkit	30
5.2.16 European Commission tools	30
6. Arctic PASSION Communication action plan	31
7. Arctic PASSION's visual identity - brand guidelines	38
7.1 Arctic PASSION logo	38
7.3 Word and PPT templates	40
7.4 Arctic PASSION icons	41
7.6 Typography	45
8. Monitoring and Evaluation of Communication Efforts	46

Executive summary

The Arctic PASSION Communication Plan explains the communications objectives for the project, defines the target audiences we will try to reach with our communication and the strategy behind outreach to each of those audiences.

It outlines all of the internal and external tools that we plan to use for communication with our target audiences, as well as a strategy behind each external tool - especially website, media outreach and social media, and specifies the roles and responsibilities of partners for communication-related activities. There is an action plan for implementing the proposed measures for reaching key target audiences.

While the internal part of our website (the intranet) is not explained in-depth here, the intended use of the intranet is explained and we would like partners to actively use it to obtain the various templates and tools which can be helpful for many to use in their own communication efforts, that we will see active use of the intranet as it was intended in order to carry out the work of this project.

Project partners will make an effort to maintain consistent expression of the Arctic PASSION brand by utilising guidelines for maintaining the look and feel of the project identity, and the impact of communication efforts will be continuously monitored using SMART indicators.

Work package 9, supported by the Project Management Office, is responsible for the implementation of the Communication plan, as well as any updates to the plan throughout the project's lifetime.

Abbreviations used in the Work Package 9 plans:

AINA – Arctic Institute of North America
AMAP– The Arctic Council's Arctic Monitoring & Assessment Programme
APECS – Association of Polar Early Career Scientists

10.12.2021

www.arcticpassion.eu

Page 5 of 48

Commented [2]: Update with newest partner list

ARCTIC
PASSION

Project: Arctic PASSION

Deliverable 9.1 – Communication Plan

AOS – Arctic Observing Summit
AOSS - Arctic Observing System of Systems
ARCSAR – H2020 project, Arctic and North Atlantic Security and Emergency Preparedness Network
ARICE – H2020 project, Arctic Research Icebreaker Consortium
AWI – The Alfred Wegener Institute, the Helmholtz Centre for Polar and Marine Research
AWI-AO - AWI's Arctic Office
BAS - British Antarctic Survey
BNSR-GCOS – Baseline Surface Radiation Network and Global Climate Observing System
CAPARDUS – H2020 project, Capacity-building in Arctic Standardisation Development
CANDAC - Canadian Network for the Detection of Change
CCADI – The Canadian Consortium for Arctic Data Interoperability
CORDIS – The European Commission's 'Community Research and Development Information Service'
CRiceS – H2020 project, Climate Relevant interactions and feedbacks: the key role of sea ice and Snow
EC – European Commission
ECR – Early Career Researchers
EEA – European Environment Agency
EAVs – Essential Arctic Variables
EO – Earth Observation
ESA – European Space Agency
EcoTip – H2020 project focusing on ecological tipping points due to climate change
ECR – Early Career Researcher
EPB – European Polar Board
EU – European Union
EuroGEO - Europe's part of the Group on Earth Observations
EuroGOOS – the European component of the Global Ocean Observing System of the Intergovernmental Oceanographic Commission of UNESCO, also known as 'IOC GOOS'.
FMI - Finnish Meteorological Institute
GEO - The Group on Earth Observations
GCRC - Greenland Climate Research Centre
GINR – Greenland Institute of Natural Resources
IASC – The Inter-Agency Standing Committee
IASSA – International Arctic Social Sciences Association
ICC – Ethical and equitable engagement
iCUPE – H2020 project
IPCC – International Panel
IPS - Indigenous Peoples Secretariat
IK – Indigenous Knowledge
ISAC – International Study of Arctic Change
ITK – Canada
JRC – The European Commission's Joint Research Centre
[KOPRI - Korea Polar Research Institute](#)
KPI – Key Performance Indicator
LK – Local Knowledge
LU – Lund University
MEPs – Members of the European Parliament
MET – Norway's meteorological organisation
NABOS - International Arctic Research Center
NCA – The Norwegian Coastal Administration (Kystverket)

Project: Arctic PASSION

Deliverable 9.1 – Communication Plan

NGO – Non-governmental organisation

[NIPR - National Institute of Polar Research, Japan](#)

NPI – Norwegian Polar Institute

PAME – The Arctic Council's working group on Protection of the Arctic Marine Environment

PP - Arctic Council Permanent Participants

RAIPON – Russian Association of Indigenous Peoples of the North

ROADS – SAON's Roadmap for Arctic Observing and Data Systems

RNA-CoObs - Research Networking Activities for Sustained Coordinated Observations of Arctic Change

SAON – Sustaining Arctic Observing Networks

SIPN2 – the Sea Ice Prediction Network–Phase 2

SMART – Indicators for measuring success that are specific, measurable, attainable, relevant and time-bound.

SNOW – Arctic and Indigenous youth

UAF – The University of Alaska Fairbanks

UKRI-BAS – UK Research and Innovation, British Antarctic Survey

ULAP– University of Lapland

UNEP – United Nations Environment Programme

UNESCO – the United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural organisation

WoA - Women of the Arctic

WMO – World Meteorological organisation

WWF – World Wildlife Foundation

YOPP - Year of Polar Prediction

1 Introduction

Arctic PASSION stands for 'Pan-Arctic Observing System of Systems (pan-AOSS): Implementing observations for societal needs'. The project aims at creating a coherent, integrated pan-AOSS, suitable for end-user needs and co-created together with local and Indigenous Peoples' Communities. Further information about the project is available at www.arcticpassion.eu.

10.12.2021

www.arcticpassion.eu

Page 7 of 48

ARCTIC
PASSION

To reach the main objective, various types of interactions between Arctic PASSION partners, rights holders and stakeholders and target groups are essential. The strategies and plans for these interactions are specified in four interrelated documents: the Communication Plan, Dissemination & Utilisation Plan, Stakeholder Engagement Plan and Education & Training Plan. This document focuses on communication. The EU defines communication as

“more than just an additional reporting burden. Europe's future economic growth and jobs will increasingly have to come from innovation in products, services and business models. With this in mind, communication about European research projects should aim to demonstrate the ways in which research and innovation are contributing to a European 'Innovation Union' and account for public spending by providing tangible proof that collaborative research adds value by:

showing how European collaboration has achieved more than would have otherwise been possible, notably in achieving scientific excellence, contributing to competitiveness and solving societal challenges;

showing how the outcomes are relevant to our everyday lives, by creating jobs, introducing novel technologies, or making our lives more comfortable in other ways;

making better use of the results, by making sure they are taken up by decision-makers to influence policy-making and by industry and the scientific community to ensure follow-up.”¹

2 Arctic PASSION's communication objectives

The Arctic PASSION Communication Plan will ensure that the project outcomes are communicated timely and widely and that the research communication will meet the communication objectives of EU¹.

¹ [Improving communication and dissemination activities beyond the scientific community \(europa.eu\)](#), page 1

The objectives of Arctic PASSION communications are to:

- Raise awareness of the project and its activities,
- Communicate Arctic PASSION results timely and widely,
- Raise awareness about the role of Indigenous knowledge and local knowledge in the Arctic,
- Raise awareness about the importance of Arctic observing systems, tools and services available for Arctic residents,
- Raise awareness about the importance and benefits of collaborations,
- Ensure that the broad range of outputs from Work Packages 1-9 are synthesized to provide new knowledge that is shared through multi-directional communication with all involved actors, and
- Increase the visibility of the EU as an Arctic actor.

To achieve these objectives, the following questions need to be asked when communicating about the project: Who, what, when, where, why and how? Who are the target groups of the information? What needs to be achieved by communicating to these groups? When and how often should the information be shared? Where should the information be shared, which channel or platform should be used? Why is this target group relevant to Arctic PASSION? How should the information be communicated – in what kind of language or format?

In this context, communication is understood as a process in which all participants are learning as much as they are providing information. Arctic PASSION will use a gender-sensitive and inclusive approach, reaching the full diversity of users.² The Communication Plan will entail a series of face-to-face and online interactions as well as a project website and communication products that are tailored to specific target groups to achieve impactful project communication and promotion. It will include a plan for project promotion at events from the international to the local level to receive inputs and to provide information to those outside the project. The project will greatly benefit from interactions during the co-creation of Pilot Services (PS) and associated workshops, as well as dialogue fora with rights- and stakeholders (Please refer to the Arctic PASSION Stakeholder Engagement Plan for the definition of the different stakeholders).

3 Arctic PASSION target audiences

The target groups of Arctic PASSION communications were identified in the proposal phase of the project, and [updated after the second year of the project](#), include:

- **Six Indigenous Peoples' partner communities and organisations representing partner communities:**
Skolt Sámi (represented by Saa'mi Nue'tt Organisation, Finland)

Commented [3]: I added the changes that we made in the Stakeholder Plan to this list, too.

Commented [4]: if we write this we need to check the whole list. I asked Michael quickly for a rough look-through. If he has some comments, I'll let you know.

Commented [5R4]: additions from Michael below.

² [Diversity, Equity and Inclusion in Arctic PASSION 19Sep2021.docx - Nextcloud \(awi.de\)](#), Page 1, paragraph 2

Inuit (represented by the Hunters Organisation and Village Council in Attu, Greenland)
Tahltan Nation (represented by Tū'deseg'chō, Wholistic Indigenous Leadership Development Society, Canada)
Inupiaq and Yupiaq (represented by Unalakleet Tribal Council and the Bering Strait School District, USA)
Gwich'in Nation (represented by the Department of Cultural Heritage with the Gwich'in Tribal Council (GTC) (Canada)
Faroeese communities (represented by Fróðskaparsetrið, Faroe Islands)

Former partners before the Russian war in Ukraine:

Chukchi, Even, Yukaghir, Dolgan (represented by Local Chapter of RAIPON and Nennen and Nutendli Indigenous Peoples' Communities, Russia)
Khanty, Mansi (represented by Save Jugra Organisation)
Skolt, Ter, Kildin Sámi (represented by House of Culture, Lovozero, Russia)

- **Additional Indigenous Peoples' communities, representatives and organisations of Indigenous Peoples**, such as [the Inuvialuit in Tuktoyaktuk/Canada](#), Permanent Participants of the [Arctic Council](#), Indigenous Peoples Secretariat
- **Indigenous Youth**
- **Local communities, representatives and organisations of local communities**, such as [the Arctic Mayors Forum](#) and local governments in Northern cities and towns in the Arctic
- **Arctic Youth**
- **Representatives of minority and vulnerable groups**
- **Policy and decision-makers:**
 - On a local and sub-national level: Arctic mayors, community leaders, local/regional authorities, local/regional governments and agencies
 - On a national level: State agencies, national ministry representatives
 - Members of the EU parliament
 - Arctic Council and its Working Groups
 - Arctic Science Ministerial + Arctic Science Funders Forum
- **European and international organisations** such as [EEA](#), [GEO](#), [EEA](#), [the Northern Forum](#), [UNEP](#), [UNESCO](#), [WMO/Global Cryosphere Watch](#), [UNESCO](#) and other environmental agencies and science policy organisations
- **Local and global non-governmental and non-profit organisations** such as [WWF](#)
- **Scientific Community:**
 - Early-career scientists
 - Science organisations such as [IASC](#), [ISAC](#), [IASC](#)
 - Research Institutes
 - [International research projects, programmes and networks such as EU Polar Cluster, ESA Polar Science Cluster, Arctic Frontiers, Arctic GOOS Regional Alliance, ArcticNet, BNSR-GCOS, CANDAC \(Canadian Network for the Detection of Change\), CCADI \(led by partner AINA\), EuroGOOS, European Commission Polar Task Force, NABOS \(UAF\), NCA, RNA-CoObs \(UAF\), T-](#)

Commented [6]: see 18 month rep

Commented [7]: remove?

Commented [8R7]: I would suggest to keep it

Formatted: Outline numbered + Level: 1 + Numbering Style: Bullet + Aligned at: 0.63 cm + Indent at: 1.27 cm

MOSAIC, SAON, SIPN2, UN Decade Collaborative Centre for Ocean Prediction, YOPP

- Research projects, programmes and networks such as Arctic Frontiers, EuroGOOS, NCA, SAON, SIPN2
- International research projects and programmes such as Arctic GOOS Regional Alliance, ArcticNet, BNSR-GCOS, CANDAC (Canadian Network for the Detection of Change), CCADI (led by partner AINA), European Commission Polar Task Force, NABOS (UAF), RNA-CoObs (UAF), T-MOSAIC, UN Decade Collaborative Centre for Ocean Prediction, YOPP
 - EU Polar Cluster
 - ESA Polar Science Cluster

- **Observation services:** Copernicus services, ESA, EuroGEO services, and other EU and national services (e.g., Norwegian, Finnish and Danish Ice services), local, regional and private meteorological services
- **Private sector** (industry & business): Arctic Economic Council, Aker Arctic, Lloyd's Register, The Nautical Institute, and international to local industry associations e.g. for tourism or regional chambers of commerce
- **Further end-users of the pilot services:** Environmental agencies, local people, modellers, users of Copernicus services, local, regional and private meteorological services, local authorities, private sector
- **Arctic PASSION consortium**
 - EU Commission (EC): Horizon 2020, EU Project Management Officer, Competence Centre on Participatory and Deliberative Democracy
 - Media: European and Arctic regional media, national and local media in Arctic countries and communities participating in the project
 - **General public:** The 'beneficiary population' in Arctic states and communities participating in the project, and European society.

Commented [9]: What was the difference to the above point "research projects, programmes..."? :D

Commented [10R9]: we can merge these two subpoints together

Formatted

Formatted: Outline numbered + Level: 1 + Numbering Style: Bullet + Aligned at: 0.63 cm + Indent at: 1.27 cm

4 Arctic PASSION’s communication strategy for each target audience

Arctic PASSION will use a variety of communication methods according to the target group and communication objectives.

Table 1. Communication strategy for each target audience

	Target audience	Purpose (Communication objectives)	Communication methods	Who communicates	When to communicate
1	6-8 Indigenous Peoples' Partner Communities and organisations representing partner communities	<p>Provide project information</p> <p>Establish trusted long-term channels of communication & provide space for effective dialogue & mutual understanding</p> <p>Understand needs with regards to observations services</p> <p>an inclusive dialogue</p>	<p>Website & Arctic Windows to the Arctic</p> <p>Co-created workshops</p> <p>Online seminars</p> <p>Materials such as Information posters about the pilot services focusing on local information and results for the specific community in local or Indigenous languages, partly on-demand</p> <p>Local radio programmes, animation and/or social media engagements</p> <p>Flyers in local languages with information relevant to a specific area/region</p>	Pilot Service Leads, Work Packages working with the Communities and supported by Work Package 9	<p>Regularly for general project communications, quarterly for focused information tailored to specific communities, and as needed.</p>
2	Indigenous communities, representatives and organisations of Indigenous communities	An inclusive pan-AOSS must include Indigenous Knowledge (IK)	Letter about Arctic Passion to the Indigenous Peoples Secretariat and the 8 individual organisations being united in	Project Management Office with support of Work Package 4 and 9	Quarterly and as needed

Commented [11]: I assume this is the 'Arctic Window'?

Commented [13]: Do we do this?

Commented [12]: Have we done this?

			the Arctic Council Permanent Participants		
3	Indigenous Youth	Arctic Youth who are school participants become project Ambassadors and will spread messages via personal outreach projects. They bring inputs back to their communities and can broaden networks and increase the involvement of local communities within the project.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Arctic PASSION and APECS websites -Arctic PASSION and APECS Social Media Channels FrostByte videos Arctic PASSION School 	Work Package 9	Regularly
4	Local communities, representatives and organisations of local communities	An inclusive pan-AOSS must include local knowledge	<p>Website & 'Arctic Windows to the Arctic'</p> <p>Co-created workshops & Webinars</p> <p>Materials such as Information posters about the pilot services focusing on local information and results for the specific community in local or indigenous languages, partly on-demand</p> <p>Local radio programmes</p>	Project Management Office with support of Work Package 4 and 9	Quarterly and as needed
5	Arctic Youth	Arctic Youth who are school participants become project Ambassadors and will spread messages via personal outreach projects. They bring inputs back to their communities and can broaden networks and increase the involvement of local communities within the project.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Arctic PASSION and APECS websites Arctic PASSION and APECS Social Media Channels Direct approaching networks e.g. Arctic Youth Network Social media 	Work Package 9	Regularly

Commented [14]: Remove Arctic Council?

Commented [15]: Was this ever done? Should it be done or perhaps removed?

Commented [16]: Same comment as above

			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> FrostByte videos Arctic PASSION School 		
6	<p>Policy and decision-makers on a sub-national level:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Arctic Mayors Arctic Council Members of EU Parliament Arctic Science Ministerial Arctic Science Funders Forum 	<p>Communicate the needs, strategies and sustainability of a pan-AOSS</p> <p>Highlight key Arctic issues</p> <p>React to needs of MEPs</p> <p>Provide space for effective dialogue</p> <p>Ensure Arctic PASSION’s contribution to global & regional science initiatives</p> <p>Dialogue for mutual learning & information</p> <p>Contribute with Arctic PASSION results to global & regional science initiatives</p> <p>Inform policymakers of the relevance of Arctic monitoring services</p> <p>Raise awareness of EU Arctic research</p> <p>Inform communities of the Arctic monitoring services & the Arctic PASSION Pilot Services</p> <p>Raise awareness of EU Arctic research</p> <p>Establish trusted channels of communication for mutual learning during the project & beyond</p>	<p>Through 2-way dialogues</p> <p>Consultation meetings</p> <p>Policy briefs</p> <p>Online survey face-to-face briefings</p> <p>External website</p> <p>Presentations at the Working Group and Permanent Participant meetings</p> <p>Project promotional materials</p> <p>Press releases & On-demand materials</p> <p>Website & ‘Arctic WindowWindows to the Arctic’</p> <p>On-demand materials</p> <p>Project promotional materials</p> <p>Policy briefs & dialogue</p> <p>Website & ‘Arctic WindowWindows to the Arctic’</p> <p>Project promotional materials</p> <p>On-demand target materials</p>	<p>Work Package 4, Work package 6, Work package 7 with support from Work Package 9</p>	<p>Regularly, as Working Group meetings are scheduled, yearly</p> <p>Biennial General Assembly</p>

Commented [17]: I think that dialogue by definition goes in 2-ways.

		<p>Ensure Arctic PASSION contributions to global & regional science initiatives</p> <p>Inform policy-makers & raise awareness of the EU involvement in the Arctic</p>	<p>Online seminars</p> <p>Policy briefs</p> <p>Conference presentations</p> <p>Press releases</p>		
7	European and International non-governmental organisations, non-profit organisations and associations	<p>Raise awareness of the usefulness of our project and project services and outputs, increase the use of the pilot services</p>	<p>Website & 'Arctic Windows to the Arctic'</p> <p>Conference presentations</p> <p>Project promotional materials</p> <p>Press releases</p>	<p>Work packages 7 and 9, supported by the Project Management Office</p>	<p>Regularly</p>
8	Scientific community:	<p>Disseminate project results & information</p> <p>Highlight the value of interdisciplinary research</p> <p>Reinforce the Arctic PASSION brand</p> <p>Strengthen recognition of EU & Arctic PASSION as state-of-the-art research</p> <p>Empower the next generation of polar scientists</p> <p>Facilitate ECR networking both within the scientific community & among ECR & stakeholders & rightsholders</p> <p>Explain and discuss the research conducted in the project with a wider audience</p>	<p>Website & 'Arctic Windows to the Arctic'</p> <p>Social media & Research blogs</p> <p>Conference presentations</p> <p>Peer-reviewed publications</p> <p>Scientific meetings & workshops</p> <p>Website APECS website & other Early Career Scientists' (ECR) networks</p> <p>Social media</p> <p>FrostByte videos</p> <p>Arctic PASSION School</p> <p>Online seminars</p>	<p>Work Package 6, Work Package 9</p>	<p>Frequently when any news or new results become available, and in connection with events</p>

9	Arctic PASSION Consortium	<p>Efficient & transparent management</p> <p>Produce a collegial working atmosphere</p> <p>Ensure cross-Work Package collaboration and feedback</p> <p>Mitigate risk & conflict fulfil project aims</p>	<p>General Assembly, Steering Committee and Work Package meetings</p> <p>Website (external & internal)</p> <p>Email updates & teleconference-</p> <p>Newsletters & social media</p>	Project Management Office, Work Package 9 and all the partners,	Regular meetings (e.g. bi-weekly or monthly), annual Assembly, as needed
10	Observation services	<p>Inform EU & national services on the project-</p> <p>Create synergies with Copernicus & other EU services & programs-</p> <p>Increase uptake of Copernicus Arctic products.</p>	<p>Website & the Arctic Window</p> <p>Press releases & On-demand materials</p> <p>Project promotional materials</p>	Work Package 4 supported by Work Package 9	
11	Private sector	<p>Inform the private sector about the relevant Arctic monitoring services & the Arctic PASSION Pilot Services</p>	<p>Website & targeted materials</p> <p>Press releases & On-demand materials</p>	Work Package 4 with support from Work Package 9	When relevant or needed
12	Further end-users of the pilot services		<p>Event activities</p> <p>Newsletter</p> <p>Arctic Window Windows to the Arctic platform</p>		
13	European Commission	<p>Raise The Profile of EU funded Arctic research</p>	<p>Website & Arctic Window Windows to the Arctic</p> <p>Press releases & On-demand materials</p> <p>Project promotional materials</p> <p>Policy brief</p>	Work Package 6-8 with support from Work Package 9	Regular EU Polar Cluster meetings and events

Commented [18]: Have we done this?

			EU Polar Cluster and other related EU events Regular contact with the Arctic PASSION Project Management Officer		
14	Media	Present project output <u>to reach and wider audiences</u> Provide popularized information to media Explain the latest research outputs & the need for a better observing system & EO uptake Strengthen recognition of the EU & Arctic PASSION as a state-of-the-art research	Website Media packages Press releases & On-demand materials FrostBytes videos & Research blogs Workshops, meetings & interviews with key stakeholders	Work Package 9 and all partners	When interesting activities are carried out or new results become available
15	General public/ Beneficiary population in Arctic states	Raise general understanding & knowledge on the state of the Arctic & advantages of Arctic Observations (AO) Raise awareness of climate change in the Arctic & impacts on Arctic communities Strengthen recognition of Arctic PASSION Raise the profile of EU funded science Increase uptake of AO products	Website & <u>Arctic Window Windows to the Arctic</u> Social Media, including. Research blogs <u>Story Maps</u> & other map products FrostByte videos Online Seminars Outreach projects & products to be developed by our Ambassadors	Work Package 9, all partners	Regularly, when relevant

Commented [19]: to wider audience?

Commented [20]: Have we done this?

Commented [21]: Are we doing this?

5 Arctic PASSION's communication tools

Arctic PASSION will utilize various tools for efficient internal communication among the project partners and external communication with project stakeholders and wider audiences.

5.1 Tools for internal communications

Internal communication will be carried out by regular face-to-face and online interactions, that include:

- Steering Committee Meetings every 2 weeks
- Regular Work Package meetings
- Task groups are created as and when needed and are composed of individuals from across work packages.
- General Assembly – an in-person meeting arranged once a year

Commented [22]: Have these been created?

In addition, information will be shared through a selection of digital tools and platforms:

- Intranet, Internal members website
- WebEx
- Microsoft Teams
- NextCloud
- Email lists
- Google calendar for internal (and external) coordination of attendance at events that are relevant for Arctic PASSION. The intention of the calendar is for project partners to coordinate attendance at activities, give an overview on our website and enable others to join.

5.1.2 Intranet

Ideally, the intranet would be the main source of information about the project for involved partners, as well as the tool most actively used internally to keep updated on news, find guidelines and other helpful project tools and documents, as well as a calendar of events planned, as well as areas for reporting impact.

5.2 Tools for external communications

Arctic PASSION utilizes digital platforms, engagement in relevant events and print-out information products for external communication. An important part of these is a unified Arctic PASSION visual branding. The following tools are currently in use or planned:

5.2.1 Website

The Arctic PASSION website is available at www.arcticpassion.eu. The website is designed to serve as a tool for both Communication and Dissemination by:

- Providing an overview of Arctic PASSION's objectives, work packages and partners
- Providing contact information for the project and its' partners
- Providing results from the project including easy access to the Pilot Services

- Providing access to the latest news from the project
- Providing a gateway to social media

The target audiences for the website are the same as the communication target audiences presented in Table 1 of this document. Arctic Youth will have its own sub-section on the website (Sharing Circle).

Commented [23]: Do we have this?

While partners are responsible for sending updated results for publication on the website and in other channels, GRID-Arendal is responsible for updating and maintenance of the website. GRID-Arendal and AWI Project Management Office in cooperation are responsible for the website's intranet. Roles and responsibilities are further outlined in the section on Roles and responsibilities.

Commented [24]: *updating and maintaining the website

Website operations and responsibilities

The Arctic PASSION website will be frequently updated so that it remains useful for the partners, collaborators and other target audiences. GRID-Arendal is maintaining the website but all the partners share the responsibility to share relevant information timely.

Tasks and responsibilities related to the website are detailed in Table 2.

Table 2. Tasks, responsibilities and timeline for keeping the website updated.

Tasks	Responsible	When
Periodic updating of website pages to reflect new information on the project	GRID-Arendal, with input from all partners as needed	2 times a year or when necessary.
Highlight new results through the 'Data portal' and 'Publications' areas of the internal website as well as in the news section of the external website.	Any partners who are lead OR contributing authors are responsible for notifying Work Package 9 of new publications and providing links to the published article. GRID-Arendal will put the news on the website	On an ongoing basis as results become available
Highlighting press releases on Arctic PASSION research with high public relevance (See Annex 8.1 on media outreach strategy)	Any partners who are the lead or contributing authors should get in touch with GRID-Arendal well in advance. GRID-Arendal will put the press release and additional material on the website	On a rolling basis (see below, media outreach responsibilities). Partners should contact GRID-Arendal at least 6 weeks in advance of expected publication so that GRID-Arendal can help prepare a press release and reach out to various media.
Highlighting external news stories on the website (See Annex 8.1 on media outreach strategy)	Any partners who are aware of or have facilitated news in external media (e.g., in newspapers, online media platforms, etc) should send the link to GRID-Arendal. GRID-Arendal will highlight the coverage the website	On an ongoing basis, as news is published
Gathering website analytics	GRID-Arendal will collect data on the number and type of visits for both reporting purposes and as a means of improving the design and functionality of the website	2 times a year, at the same time as website updates

5.2.2 Mailing lists

Arctic PASSION maintains contact lists for both internal project partners and external guests and collaborating partners associated with the project. These lists will take into account the EU's General Data Protection Regulation.

5.2.3 Social media

Arctic PASSION will develop content primarily for three platforms: Facebook, Twitter and Instagram. In addition, LinkedIn and Youtube channels have been established and are used when feasible; for instance, when there are relevant job postings or videos that have been created. An Arctic PASSION page has been created for Facebook, which is useful for sharing results, announcing events and updating the project's community of followers. Messages will also be prepared for Twitter, although we rely on the partners to share information through their own channels. The Twitter account for Arctic PASSION is useful for staying connected with our partners and keeping each other updated on events. The channels will be monitored and their use will be assessed every month. Arctic PASSION likes and follows the EU Polar Cluster channels to further promote the work and to collaborate.

Commented [25]: The way I see it LinkedIn is used more than Facebook. I also got the impression that facebook was created as a way to reach out to more Indigenous although we are not getting a lot of attractions on FB posts.

Social media strategy

The project aims to use social media channels strategically and follow the guidance by EU³. Arctic PASSION uses channels on which the most important target groups are most active (e.g. EU, Arctic Council WGs), see a detailed overview [here](#).

The goal of using social media is to reach out to diverse target groups and increase awareness of the project as well as to increase uptake of the project's pilot services and other results of the project. The goal is to share our information and news at the exact moment they are taking place, for example:

- When we have a project breakthrough, reach a genuine milestone or get results
- When we are presenting our project at an event
- When a new press release is published

Mapping relevant social media channels

A Communications survey conducted in September 2021 in association with the Arctic PASSION project's kick-off was carried out to map the communication channels that Arctic PASSION members use for different purposes in September 2021. There were 46 respondents who identified themselves as Senior within Academia/Science, 19 male, 15 female and who

³ https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/other/grants_manual/amga/soc-med-guide_en.pdf

also specified that Twitter, Facebook and email were their preferred social media channels of communication for the project.

In addition, social media channels used by all partners organisations have been investigated, and results show that while 31% of partners use all five commonly used social media platforms (Facebook, Twitter, Instagram, YouTube and LinkedIn), 60% of partners use 3 or more of these channels, mainly Facebook, Twitter and Youtube, although Instagram is just as much used as Youtube among partners and collaborators. The overview is available [here](#). The EU states that "EU-funded projects mostly use Twitter, Facebook, LinkedIn, Google+, Instagram and Pinterest (with most preferring Twitter)."⁴Arctic PASSION is currently mapping the best ways to reach out to the Arctic communities, and the social media strategy will be updated accordingly.

Different social media channels can be used to reach specific target audiences. For instance, Facebook can be effective in reaching students, scientists, organisations working on climate or Arctic issues and engaged citizens, as well as Indigenous Peoples' Communities; Twitter can be effective in reaching policymakers in Europe and the Arctic working on climate and environment; Instagram can also be effective in reaching scientists, the wider public and Arctic Youth; YouTube can reach Arctic Youth and the wider public; and LinkedIn is more professionally-focused channel targeting scientists, experts, policymakers and organisations. Further guidelines for partners to follow when posting on any of the social media channels are provided in 'Social media guidelines' included in the Communications toolkit on the intranet.

The social media channels are maintained by GRID-Arendal. New Arctic PASSION posts are drafted according to inputs from partners and reviewed by the Project Management Office (Table 3). Although partners can publish their own posts tagging Arctic PASSION without any review or approval from the project.

Commented [26]: ???

Table 3. Use of social media according to the target audiences

Channel	Arctic PASSION handle	Type of content	Target audience	Frequency
 Facebook	@arcticpassion	Text, images, videos, links, stories, live stream	Indigenous Communities / other remote communities / wider public	Once a month and/or when needed
 Twitter	@arctic_passion	Text, up to 280 characters	Policy-makers / wider public	Min. once a week, more often during events

⁴ [soc-med-guide_en.pdf \(europa.eu\)](#), page 6

	arctic_passion	Images, videos, stories, live stream	Scientists, the wider public, Arctic Youth	Once a week or when needed
	Arctic PASSION	Text, photos, videos, links	Scientists, experts, policymakers, organisations	When needed
	Arctic PASSION	Audio-visual content	Wider public, Arctic Youth	When Arctic PASSION video material published

Commented [27]: I don't think we have managed this once a week

Social media roles and responsibilities

All partners involved in the project are encouraged to actively use social media to promote the activities and results of Arctic PASSION, and it is their responsibility to ensure that their posts are tagged correctly so that it is associated with the project. However, social media posts from the official Arctic PASSION channels are the responsibility of Work Package 9, more specifically GRID-Arendal who is maintaining the sites, with support from the Project Management Office, AWI-APECS and Work Package 4 when necessary, such as where posts are concerning politically, culturally or other sensitive topics.

Table 4 . Roles and responsibilities of partners in social media posting

Tasks	Responsible	When
Create social media accounts	GRID-Arendal	September 2021
Develop social media content for the Arctic PASSION accounts	GRID-Arendal, with input and participation from all partners and their respective institutional media focal points	When new results or notable news from the project is available
Develop social media content concerning or tagging #ArcticPASSION	All project partners	Ongoing
Create a list of contacts responsible for social media at all partner institutions	GRID-Arendal with input from all partners	By February of 2022
Monitor impact and analytics	GRID-Arendal in collaboration with partners institutions	Every month

Commented [28]: Do we have this?

Commented [29]: I think the analytics are monitored with the reporting and not every month

Technical information – for publishing

In any public product, the use of the EU emblem including the grant number is required in order to acknowledge the European Commission as the funder of the project.

The emblem only should always be used, and the text about funding where possible.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 101003472

Several versions of the EU emblem and logo exist, depending on the purpose for which it is needed. Please refer to [the official guidelines for using the EU emblem](#) for further clarification.

The EU specifies:

All communication related to the project (including electronic communication, using social media, etc.) and all infrastructure, equipment or major results funded under the grant must: (a) display the EU emblem

Commented [30]: This is not done for all communications

and (b) include the following text: This project has received funding from the [European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme] [Euratom research and training programme 2014-2018] under grant agreement No [number].⁵

5.2.4 Media outreach

Press releases are part of the overall media outreach strategy and will be developed in advance of any notable publications to get the word out to the media. Press releases, as well as a series of royalty-free photos and other material including illustrations and maps, will be made available through a media package for Arctic PASSION. The media package will be housed on the Arctic PASSION website in the "Contact" section.

Commented [31]: Same comment as before

At a minimum, the media package will contain

- 1) an illustration explaining the Arctic PASSION processes
- 2) a map explaining the project activity areas
- 3) general project flyer or fact sheet
- 4) contact information

⁵ [soc-med-guide_en.pdf \(europa.eu\)](#), page 5

Media outreach strategy

Media outlets are an important channel through which to reach a number of our target audiences, including scientists, policymakers and the general public. The project will work to earn media exposure for Arctic PASSION as a whole and for its specific research projects, papers, and results. By getting coverage of Arctic PASSION in different types of media outlets, we can reach different types of audiences, including scientists, policymakers, and the general public. GRID-Arendal will lead the media strategy, but active participation from all partners and their institutions is needed to make the strategy successful.

Key activities:

- Identify high-priority media outlets and **establish a line of contact with relevant journalists and editors** (see details below)^[KHF1]
- Developing and updating an activity and publication calendar. Work package 9 will identify early on the 'windows of opportunities' – field trips, expeditions, speeches, workshops etc – that might be of interest to different local/national/regional media outlets and plan proactively for their possible participation. Work package 9 will work actively to share not only the end results of the research but invite relevant media to also follow and document the research in its various stages.^[KHF2]
 - Work Package 9 needs to be well prepared internally to understand what notable new activities are being launched and what results are being made publicly available, when, and by whom.
 - Partners should make GRID-Arendal aware of new activities, forthcoming articles, or major results at least two to three months in advance of launch or planned publication.
- Writing and distributing press releases
 - GRID-Arendal will work to prepare press releases and other promotional materials as needed, coordinating with press offices in partner institutions to the extent possible.
 - GRID-Arendal will have an initial meeting with the researcher(s) to discuss the forthcoming publication, main points to be communicated, people to be quoted, photos or graphics to be shared, etc.
 - GRID-Arendal, researchers, and their institutions' press offices will collaborate to write, edit, and finalize the press release.
 - GRID-Arendal will distribute press releases through Eurek!Alert, through the Arctic PASSION website and social media accounts, and through relevant email lists.
 - Partner institution press offices will distribute press releases to their networks and contacts.
- Conducting outreach to journalists

Commented [32]: Have we been following this plan of reaching out to media outlets?

- GRID-Arendal will share press releases or other information directly with journalists whose work encompasses Arctic PASSION topics.
- Partner institution press offices will do outreach to their networks and contacts.
- Sharing some videos or photos from field trips or from the researchers themselves
- Distributing a list of expert contacts that journalists can contact if they are interested in knowing more about the project
- Hosting or live streaming events which might be of interest to media and which they should be invited to early on
- Partnering up with journalists for moderating or coverage of these events
- Invitations to join specific field trips or expeditions that could produce great visuals that would be of extra interest for TV teams or photographers
- Hosting journalists to directly observe Arctic PASSION work
 - GRID-Arendal will collaborate with partner institutions to identify good opportunities for in-person engagement with journalists, e.g., inviting them to attend a research-related event.
 - GRID-Arendal will coordinate any in-person journalist visits and do follow-ups.
- Preparing researchers to talk with journalists
 - When journalists are interested in reporting on Arctic PASSION, GRID-Arendal can work with researchers to develop talking points and prepare for interviews.
 - Such a training programme can be considered for the early-career training workshop
- Supporting researchers in advance to talk with journalists
 - When journalists are interested in reporting on Arctic PASSION, GRID-Arendal can work with researchers to develop talking points and prepare to be interviewed.
 - See also Arctic PASSION Education and Training Plan

Potential News Outlets to Target

GRID-Arendal will do outreach to a variety of news outlets to let them know about Arctic PASSION's work and published research. In addition to collaborating with institutions' press offices and targeting their networks of media contacts, GRID-Arendal will contact journalists at outlets such as the ones below. These lists will grow and evolve as the Arctic PASSION project progresses, and as partners share their contacts and recommendations.

- Science news outlets:
 - Target publications could include [Science News](#), [Science News for Students](#), [New Scientist](#), Popular Science, The Conversation, Horizon Magazine, [ScienceDaily](#), Live Science, Undark, National Geographic
 - [United Academics Magazine](#), [Scientific American](#), [Science](#), [Sci News](#), [Phys Org](#).
- European general and environmental news outlets:
 - Target publications could include The Economist, [The Guardian](#) - Europe, [Politico EU](#), Climate Home News, Carbon Brief, ClimateNews Network, [BBC News Europe](#), [Euronews](#), [Aljazeera Europe news](#), [CNN Europe](#), [Reuters](#), [BBC Science & Environment](#), [Environmental News Network](#), [The Guardian - Environment](#), [PEER: Partnership for European Environmental Research](#)
- Arctic general and environmental news outlets:
 - Target publications could include [Arctic Today](#), [Eye on the Arctic](#), Arctic Portal News Portlet, [The Guardian - Arctic](#), [BBC News -Arctic](#), [Over the Circle](#), [eco environment coastal and offshore](#)
 - Regional Arctic news outlets: [Global news](#) (Canada), [Nunatsiq News](#) (Canada), [The Arctic Sounder](#) (Alaska), [Anchorage Daily News](#) (Alaska), [The Arctic](#) (Russian and English), [The Barents Observer](#) (Russia, Norway), [High North News \(Norway\)](#), [yle news](#) (Finland), [CBC News - Indigenous](#); The Arctic Today
 - Arctic journalists: [Arctic bureau freelance journalist contacts](#)
- Earth observation news outlets: [Space News](#), [BBC News - earth observation](#), [Innovation news network](#), [euronews - earth observation](#), [Meteorological Technology International](#)
- News outlets in the [6 & 8-Indigenous Peoples' Partner Communities, such as: Inuit Tapiriit Kanatami](#), [Indigenous Khanty community of the Bolsheï Yugan River in western Siberia](#), [The Northern Forum](#), [ELOKA: Exchange for Local Observations and Knowledge of the Arctic](#),

Media outreach responsibilities

An important part of the project’s communication activities involves creating an effective network of media contacts and making use of this network for more efficient communication. The main tasks and responsibilities for media outreach are listed in Table 4.

Table 5. Media outreach responsibilities

Tasks	Responsible	When
Calendar of activities and publications	Work Package 9 with input from partners	December 2021 for the initial calendar; updates will be ongoing
Publications overview and calendar (Excel sheet tracking deliverables, plans for communication/dissemination and related events)	PO supported by GRID-Arendal	Ongoing
Create an initial media list of outlets and journalists to contact	GRID-Arendal with input from partners	December 2021 for initial list; updates will be ongoing
Write press releases	GRID-Arendal in collaboration with researchers and partner institution press offices	When notable news or papers are published

Commented [33]: needs to be updated

Commented [34R33]: @sabrinaheerema@gmail.com , can you update this please?

Direct outreach to reporters	GRID-Arendal in collaboration with partner institutions press offices	When notable new papers are published or other events create opportunities
Arranging media visits or trips to research sites	GRID-Arendal in collaboration with researchers and partners	When good opportunities arise
Monitoring news to find outlets and journalists covering our issues	GRID-Arendal	ongoing

5.2.5 Roll-ups, flyers and posters

Roll-ups and posters will be created for Arctic PASSION based on specific expressed needs from partners, for example ahead of important events. A general Arctic PASSION flyer will also be produced, depending on expressed need. In addition, a short project fact sheet (one-pager) answering:

- o Why Arctic PASSION exists
- o When Arctic PASSION was launched
- o The goals and tasks of Arctic PASSION
- o Why Arctic PASSION is special and unique
- o The kind of work/service Arctic PASSION conducts and provides
- o The main activities
- o The main achievements
- o How Arctic PASSION benefits the EU and Arctic citizens

will be developed in early 2022 in digital and paper form. Additional fact sheets such as a general sheet on Arctic observations will be developed as needed.

5.2.6 International conferences, events, workshops and stakeholder meetings

Arctic PASSION will be promoted at Arctic, European and international conferences – in-person and virtual – throughout the project. This will be done, for example, by joint booths with other EU Cluster projects at Arctic Circle, AOS / ASSW and other relevant events in cooperation with Work Package 6. Arctic PASSION will engage in a number of possible events from 2021-2025 and a selection of candidate events is included below in Table 6 as an example of a table that will be made available to the partners on the Intranet. This information will be added to the Arctic PASSION calendar which will be updated regularly and will provide a good planning tool to see what communication support can be provided by Work package 9.

Table 6. A tentative list of relevant upcoming events of interest to Arctic PASSION.

Event	Role/Institutions present (if known)	Date (if known)	Frequency if applicable
Arctic Frontiers		End of January	Yearly
Arctic Observing Summit		End of March	Bi-annually
Arctic Science Summit Week		End of March	
EGU General Assembly		End of April yearly	Yearly
EuroGEO Annual meeting/conference		May	
GEO Symposium		mid-June	

Commented [35]: Needs update

International Conference on Permafrost (ICOP)		mid-June	
Polar Data Forum		end of September	
Arctic Circle		October	Yearly
European Polar Science Week	EU Polar Cluster representation	October	
European Conference on Permafrost (EUCOP)		end of October	
GEO Week		November	
EU Arctic Forum and Indigenous Peoples' dialogue in Brussels	Participation by Project Management Office	10-11 Nov	
GTN-P		mid-November	
Polar Data Architecture workshop		end of November	
IASS workshop on Ethics and Methods in Arctic Transformative Research	AWI-Arctic Office presentation	25-26 November 2021	
Sharing Circle on Arctic wildland fires (from CAFF and EPPR Working Groups of the Arctic Council)		17-18 November 2021	
Arctic Council Senior Arctic Official meetings	Presentation by the Arctic Office on Arctic PASSION	1-2 December 2021	twice a year
AGU Fall Meeting	Scientific presentation by Arctic PASSION partners	mid-December	Yearly
IMO workshops		ongoing	
Arctic Council Working Group Meetings		TBC	1-2 times a year
EU Polar Cluster meetings		TBC	Monthly
ESA Polar Cluster meetings			yearly

5.2.7 EU Polar Cluster

Arctic PASSION is part of the EU Polar Cluster of projects: <https://www.polarcluster.eu>. The EU Polar Cluster is a collaboration of EU-funded members. It's aim is to be a strong, well-connected ecosystem of European Polar projects and organisations operating together to substantially increase their combined impact and legacy. The Cluster thus merges a broad spectrum of research and coordination activities-ranging from the most up-to-date findings on permafrost and sea ice, from enhancing observation to improving predictions, and from networking research stations to coordinating access to icebreakers.⁶ The added value for Arctic PASSION to be part of the cluster includes:

- Higher impacts from collective projects' efforts
- Increased knowledge sharing
- Better engagement with stakeholders

⁶ [Home - EU Polar Cluster](#)

- Greater visibility
- Better use of citizens' money

One of the principal means for Arctic PASSION to engage with the Cluster is through its Communications Task Group, which meets every two months. The Cluster is coordinated through EU Polar Net 2 through the Arctic PASSION Work Package₆ co-lead. In addition, a deliverable of Arctic PASSION is to create a new Task Group on Observations.

5.2.8 Targeted briefings for policymakers

Face to face meetings are an important dissemination tool and Arctic PASSION will use these where necessary. Table 1 within the Dissemination and Utilisation Plan provides an overview of the possible face to face briefings. In addition, printed policy briefings are produced when needed.

5.2.9 Training activities

Arctic PASSION will organise a workshop for early-career researchers on how to better communicate their work to non-scientists. The exact format and its location (e.g., as a summer course in the field or back-to-back with a conference) will be developed over the course of the first year of the project. Storytelling and media training for early-career scientists is tentatively planned for 2022. (see Arctic PASSION Education and Training Plan)

Commented [36]: Update with Sharing Circle?

5.2.10 Videos and vlogs

A proactive link between GEO communication by the GEO secretariat and Arctic PASSION communication for Arctic-GEOSS will be established. Stories manifesting the development of the new Arctic services will be deployed on Arctic-GEOSS.org in collaboration with Work Package₆.

5.2.11 ~~Windows to the Arctic~~ Arctic Window platform

GRID-Arendal will lead the development of the ~~Arctic Window~~ ~~Windows to the Arctic~~ website – an interactive online gateway to Arctic PASSION Pilot Services and other relevant Arctic information such as Arctic Copernicus data ('The Arctic window of Copernicus'). The website will be ~~co-developed with various stakeholders and rights holders~~ to make it a useful tool for the end-users. ~~The Windows to the Arctic Window~~ will include an interactive multimedia platform, ~~incorporating Indigenous, local and traditional knowledge, and scientific data~~. The aim is to increase the overall impact of Arctic PASSION by providing information about the societal and economic value of an Arctic observing network and links to the Pilot Services and by increasing ownership and usage of the services by stakeholders via co-creation of various elements for the platform. The platform will be co-developed by the Pilot Service developers, ECRs, Indigenous and local knowledge holders and community members involved in CBM. The elements may consist of animations, comics, videos, or dissemination products in other digital formats, and may visualize the connection between the outputs from a pan-AOSS with the socio-economic benefits and link them with the relevant SDGs depending upon the outcomes of the co-design process. ~~Arctic Windows to the Arctic~~ and the multimedia platform can be accessed through the Arctic PASSION website.

Commented [37]: Are we doing this?

5.2.12 Arctic PASSION Newsletter and other newsletters

Our quarterly project newsletter will provide partners, rights- and stakeholders and the general public with relevant information regarding Arctic PASSION activities and developments, including highlighting important results that have been published. Articles will be also submitted to other relevant newsletters, such as EU Polar Cluster, EUPolarNet2, INTERACT, JUST NORTH, and SAON, and to the EU Polar Cluster newsletters.

5.2.13 Online seminars

See Arctic PASSION Education and Training Plan for details.

5.2.14 Stakeholder meetings

See Arctic PASSION Stakeholder Engagement Plan for details.

5.2.15 Communications toolkit

The communications toolkit is available for the project partners through Arctic PASSION Intranet and it provides communications templates to all partners including:

- Slide show presentations
- Poster presentations
- Social media posts
- News articles
- Upcoming event attendance
- Arctic PASSION visual guidelines

5.2.16 European Commission tools

Arctic PASSION will make use of existing European Commission tools designed to maximise the impact of Horizon 2020 project Communication, such as the Research and Innovation success stories, the CORDIS portal, Horizon magazine and through application for the Horizon Impact Award.⁷

Arctic PASSION uses the EU Polar Cluster's Catalyst platform to disseminate publications and event news, as well as for thematic discussion groups. We are also collaboratively working with the European Commission's Horizon Results Booster platform on boosting communication and dissemination activities to maximize the impact of the project. The services include a portfolio and dissemination and exploitation strategy; Business plan development and preparing research for commercialisation.

⁷ [quick-guide_diss-expl_en.pdf \(europa.eu\)](#), page 2

6. Arctic PASSION Communication action plan

Arctic PASSION Communication action plan specifies timelines and responsibilities of the specific communication platforms, and their target audiences (Table 7).

English is used for internal and external communication. However, the local languages are used when possible and/or necessary in communication with the Indigenous Peoples' Communities and local communities, Arctic PASSION members facilitate the translation and translation services are hired where needed.

Table 7. Communication plan

HOW? Measure	WHO? Target audience	WHAT? Objective and message	WHERE?	WHEN?	BY WHOM? Responsible partner
Project gatherings	Arctic PASSION Consortium Collaborators	Give an updated overview on project activities and progress; Highlight results of the project; Identify synergies as well as potential risks	Online, in person when feasible	Bi-weekly Steering Committee meetings Monthly work package meetings; Yearly general assembly	Project Management Office
Website (external)	All project stakeholders	Ensure that the beneficiary population is aware of the roles of partners and of the EU in the activity	Online	Regular updates, min. bi-annually	GRID-Arendal
Website (internal)	Arctic PASSION Consortium	Share updates, documents, templates, guidelines and toolkits	Online	Regular updates, min. bi-annually	GRID-Arendal, AWI Project Management Office
Arctic PASSION newsletter	All project stakeholders	Share news on project activities and progress; Highlight results of the project	By email	Quarterly	GRID-Arendal

Project: Arctic PASSION
 Deliverable 9.1 – Communication Plan

Social media posts on Facebook, Twitter, YouTube, Instagram	Arctic PASSION Consortium and collaborative partners Beneficiary population Scientific community		Research blogs Story maps reels, videos FrostByte videos Online seminars Outreach projects & products	Regularly, min. once a week, as needed	GRID-Arendal
Social media posts on selected social media	Indigenous Peoples' Communities participating in the project		On selected social media channels according to the response from the communities	As needed	Snowchange with support from GRID-Arendal
Tailored letter / email message	Indigenous Peoples' Communities participating in the project	About the project	By email or letter	Early December 2021	Project Management Office / AWI
Digital and print-out flyers and posters tailored for the local context	Indigenous Peoples' Communities participating in the project	This is what is happening in the project's pilot services for fire, historical change, permafrost, lake ice (and other services at later stages)	Posters tailored for specific geographical areas, in the local language(s)	Spring 2022, then quarterly or as often as needed to keep updated	Snowchange with support from GRID-Arendal and Project Management Office

Co-created workshops & Online seminars	Project stakeholders	Co-creation of knowledge, exchange of information	Online, in-person in selected locations if feasible	On need basis	All Work Packages according to their objectives and work plan coordinated by the Project Management Office and Work Package9
Project reporting & Policy briefs	EU Project Management Officer Members of the European parliament				Project Management Office and Work Package 7 with Work Package 9
Arctic Window	Copernicus & other EU services Members of the European parliament Policy & science policy organisations The general public, especially the beneficiary population in Arctic	Ensure that the beneficiary population is aware of the roles of partners and of the EU in the activity Share overview and access to the Pilot Services Share stories			Work Package 4 Pilot Service leads with input from relevant other Work Packages, together with Project Management Office and Work Package 9

states and communities participating in the project				
Press releases	Copernicus & other EU services Policy & science policy organisations Private sector Media	Share news about progress, results and new services and data		GRID-Arendal, Project Management Office, all partners
Project promotion materials: roll-ups, flyers	Copernicus & other EU services Members of the European parliament Policy & science policy organisations beneficiary population		January 2022	GRID-Arendal with support from all partners
Conference presentations	Scientific community Policy-makers Arctic PASSION Consortium	New articles, scientific papers and presentations in scientific conferences		All partners

Peer-reviewed publications	Scientific community				All partners
Media packages	Media	About the project, ongoing results and impact of the project, testimonies from end-users of the pilot services	Press releases & On-demand materials FrostBytes videos & Research blogs Workshops, meetings & interviews with key stakeholders & rights holders	Project start, mid-term, and end	GRID-Arendal and APECS with support from the Project Management Office
Targeted and on-demand materials	Private sector				Respective Work Packages, including Pilot Services
Communication targeted specifically towards Arctic youth	Arctic PASSION Ambassadors Polar ECS Arctic youth	Separate email list Separate newsletter Separate workshops Engage in social media Use for media outreach Use for specific events	Website, APECS website, & other early career researchers' networks Social media Research blogs & Wiki	APECS, GRID-Arendal, with support from all partners	

		Provide media training for them	FrostByte videos & Arctic PASSION School		
Newsletter	All stakeholders	A survey conducted in September 2021 at the project's kick-off was completed by 46 respondents who indicated that they would like a project newsletter.	<p>Sent by email with links to news stories published on the website or contributed by partners.</p> <p>Also mentioned in other EU Polar Cluster newsletters.</p>	quarterly	GRID-Arendal with support from all partners

7. Arctic PASSION’s visual identity - brand guidelines

Arctic PASSION’s visual identity will be fostered throughout all communication and dissemination activities of the project. The logo, the website and all the products stemming from the project will adopt this visual identity. This effective branding will help to build the visibility and reputation of Arctic PASSION and its results.

Arctic PASSION’s visual identity consists of a series of consistent graphical elements which will be used across all communication products during the lifetime of the project, helping Arctic PASSION to be recognizable.

Consistent expression of the Arctic PASSION brand is being achieved by the usage of the following guidelines. These guidelines define what makes the Arctic PASSION brand and explain how to create the look and feel of Arctic PASSION’s identity.

7.1 Arctic PASSION logo

The logo will be used on all Arctic PASSION communication products including presentations by partners at events. All partners are encouraged to use the logo in any correspondence (e.g. email signatures) while working on the project. A high-resolution version of the logo is available for partners on the intranet.

Primary Logos

Always use the master artwork files and never try to re-create the logo or change it in any way.

The blue logo should only be used on backgrounds that are bright enough to display the logo properly. Do not put it onto a dark background.

The white logo should only be used on backgrounds that are dark enough to display the logo properly. Do not put it onto a light background.

Secondary Logos

The secondary logo should only be used in circumstances when the content around the logo is minimal.

The blue logo should only be used on backgrounds that are bright enough to display the logo properly. Do not put it onto a dark background.

The white logo should only be used on backgrounds that are dark enough to display the logo properly. Do not put it onto a light background.

Exclusion Zone

The recommended exclusion zone around the logo is shown here. The minimum clear space is equal to the height of the letter T.

Type and other graphics should never encroach on this minimum exclusion zone.

Examples Of Logo Usage

In the report above:
 The primary logo is used due to text elements beneath.
 No type or graphics is entering the exclusion zone.

In the poster above:
 The secondary logo is used since there's few elements around the logo.
 No type or graphics is entering the exclusion zone.

In the poster above:
 The primary logo in white is used since there's a lot of elements in the poster and the background is dark, therefore the white logo file is a better fit.
 No type or graphics are entering the exclusion zone.

Examples Of Misuse

Always use the master logo files. It is important that the logo is never altered. Shown here are a few simple things to avoid.

Do not place type or graphics inside the exclusion zone.

Do not place the blue primary or secondary logo on a dark colored background.

Do not place the white primary or secondary logo on a light colored background.

Do not change the color of the logo to a color that's not specified in this manual.

Do not separate the wordmark from the globe.

Do not stretch the logo or add perspective.

Do not add any effects to the logo, i.e. drop shadows.

Do not tint the logo.

7.3 Word and PPT templates

A series of Microsoft Word and Powerpoint templates have been developed and provided to the partners as a part of a Communication Toolkit available on the Intranet. All partners are encouraged to use these templates in written correspondence; as a cover page for deliverables; and when presenting Arctic PASSION to various target groups.

7.4 Arctic PASSION icons

A set of thematic icons will be included in the Communication Toolkit. These icons represent different aspects of the Arctic PASSION work, such as Arctic animals and field research. The icons can be used on the Arctic PASSION presentations and knowledge products when relevant.

7.5 Colours

To use the designated Arctic PASSION colours,

- in Word: Double-click or highlight the text > Colours > more colours > custom > type in the number of the colour > OK
For opacity: Double-click or highlight the text > Colours > Gradient > Other gradients > Adjust the transparency (in reverse)
- in Powerpoint: Double-click on or highlight your text > font colours > more colours > custom > type in the number of the colour > Enter
- in Google Docs: Click on Text-colour > click the '+' on custom, type in the number of the colour palette that you want to use, then apply this colour to your text

Primary Color Palette

The use of these colors in the communication helps build brand awareness among Arctic Passion's target audience.

The colors that have specified percentage may be used as solid colors (100%) or in the permitted tint values shown here (20%, 40%, 60% 80%). Using tints helps extend the color palette for illustrations and information graphics that needs visual differentiation.

Secondary Color Palette

A set of secondary colors has been developed for use in illustrations and information graphics. These colors should be used minimally as details.

Iron Gray should be used for text.

Primary Color Palette In Use

These are examples on how the primary color palette may be used.

Secondary Color Palette In Use

These are examples on how the secondary color palette may be used.

7.6 Typography

To use the designated Arctic PASSION fonts,

- in Word: double-click on the font > type in the name of the desired font
- in Powerpoint: Double-click on the text > Double-click on the fonts box > Type in the font name
- in Google Docs: Fonts > more fonts > type in the name of the font

if not available use the downloaded font

Install fonts: this pc, windows, fonts, copy and paste into the fonts folder

Neo Sans W1G - Primary Typeface

Arctic Passion's main typeface is Neo Sans W1G

In general, Light and Regular should be used in body copy.

Medium and Bold should be used to highlight key information or provided emphasis, when needed.

When using Microsoft Office Suite, we revert to our system typeface, Open Sans (see next page)

Aa
Neo Sans W1G
Light

A B C D E F G H I J
K L M N O P Q R S T
U V W X Y Z Æ Ø Å
1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9

Aa
Neo Sans W1G
Regular

A B C D E F G H I J
K L M N O P Q R S T
U V W X Y Z Æ Ø Å
1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9

Aa
Neo Sans W1G
Medium

A B C D E F G H I J
K L M N O P Q R S T
U V W X Y Z Æ Ø Å
1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9

Aa
Neo Sans W1G
Bold

A B C D E F G H I J
K L M N O P Q R S T
U V W X Y Z Æ Ø Å
1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9

Open Sans - System Typeface

In some applications it may not be possible to use Neo Sans W1G.
In that case, Arctic Passion uses the free system typeface: Open Sans.

Aa
Open Sans
Light

A B C D E F G H I
J K L M N O P Q R S
T U V W X Y Z Æ Ø
Å 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9

Aa
Open Sans
Regular

A B C D E F G H I J
K L M N O P Q R S T
U V W X Y Z Æ Ø Å
1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9

Aa
Open Sans
Semi-bold

A B C D E F G H I J
K L M N O P Q R S T
U V W X Y Z Æ Ø Å
1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9

Aa
Open Sans
Bold

A B C D E F G H I J
K L M N O P Q R S T
U V W X Y Z Æ Ø Å
1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9

8. Monitoring and Evaluation of Communication Efforts

Work package 9 will take the overall lead in collecting important statistics and key performance indicators when it comes to Communication efforts, while partners are all responsible for

tracking information and providing input on their own activities. The project's Key Performance indicators are presented in Table 8. Indicators the project will monitor are specific, measurable, attainable, relevant, and time-bound (SMART).

Table 8. Quantitative and qualitative Arctic PASSION Key Performance Indicators and responsibilities for monitoring them.

Key Performance Indicator	Specific indicator	Roles/Responsibilities
KPI 1: Online communications reach, (social) media footprint	Number of website unique visitors/unique visits/page views over a given time period	Work Package ₉ with input from partners
	Audience statistics for both print and online media reach (on other platforms)	Work Package ₉ with input from partners
	Number of people asking for more information	All partners
	<u>Quantitative: Facebook, instagram, Twitter, YouTube and LinkedIn analytics/analytics, number of followers, number of views, likes, re-shares, interactions, total reach or impressions.</u>	<u>Work package 9</u>
	<u>Qualitative: reactions, tone of comments, categories of followers (such as Indigenous Youth or Indigenous Peoples) and post responders/viewers.</u>	
	<u>Twitter Analytics: Quantitative indicators such as the number of clicks, likes, shares, tags, video views, new followers, profile visits, engagement rates, cost per result, use of #ArcticPASSION hashtag and influence of the accounts that use it, etc.</u>	<u>Work Package 9</u>
	<u>Instagram and Facebook Insights: Quantitative indicators such as the number of clicks, likes, shares, tags, video views, new followers, profile visits, engagement rates, cost per result, use of #ArcticPASSION hashtag and influence of the accounts that use it, etc.</u> <u>Qualitative indicators such as types of comments received, their tone, the number of people they reached, the types of followers, impressions, traffic data, ratings, word clouds etc.</u>	<u>Work Package 9</u>
KPI 2: Face-to-face meetings	<u>Quantitative:</u> The number of people attending or participating in events including presentations, public lectures, seminars, etc.	Project Management Office, all partners responsible for gathering estimates of the number of people attending events (in person or online)—will be collated by Work Package 9

Formatted Table

Formatted Table

Project: Arctic PASSION
 Deliverable 9.1 – Communication Plan

	Qualitative indicators:; who were participating; age groups; position/rank;	
	Qualitative: who were participating; age groups, position/rank, direct feedback on impact made/understanding changed through direct feedback, i.e. through a survey.	
KPI 3: The usefulness of a specific communications products for selected, main target audiences, -such as Indigenous Peoples' Partner Communities.	Qualitative feedback from the target groups in the format the target audiences prefer.	Work package 9 together with other work packages, and focal points of the audiences or co-creators, such as local Indigenous Peoples' Community contacts and work package 4 snowchange
KPI 43 : Collaboration and synergies	Number of partners engaged in activities led by or co-organised by Arctic PASSION	All partners, Work Package 9 will collate
	Number of cluster activities sponsored/co-organised	All partners, Work Package 9 will collate
	Number of events attended by project members	Work Package 10
	The nature of the above events: type, size, targeted community	Work Package 10
KPI 54 : Media footprint	The number of Arctic PASSION appearances in various media outlets/articles in the press, can be online but not included under the 'social media' category, for example, the digital version of a local newspaper.	Work Package 9, Work Package 10
	Number of debates in the media	Work Package 9, Work Package 10

